

Research Article

Effect of Leaf Clipping on Morphological Features and Yield in Mungbean Genotypes

A. Naznin¹, N. Haque², R. Sarker³, M.S.I. Rion⁴ and M. M. Rahman^{3*}

¹ Senior Scientific Officer, Soil Resource Development Institute, District Office, Kushtia, Bangladesh

² Department of Crop Botany, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh-2202

³ Scientific Officer (Horticulture), Spices Research Sub-Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, Faridpur, Bangladesh

⁴ Department of Agricultural Chemistry, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh-2202

*Corresponding Author

Email: musfiqur.bari@gmail.com

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Abstract: The research aimed to investigate the effect of leaf clipping on growth, flower production, and yield of mungbean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) Wikzek). A field experiment was carried out in four mungbean genotypes viz. BINA moog-5, Mutant E4I-915, Mutant N2M-402, and BINA moog-7. The leaf clipping levels of 0%, 33%, and 66% imposed at the vegetative stages (40 days after sowing) in all four genotypes. The morphological, reproductive, and yield attributes estimated in the study had shown substantial differences for the leaf clipping treatments in all four mungbean genotypes. Leaf area, leaf dry weight, stem dry weight, total dry matter, plant height, number of branches per plant, number of open flowers/plant, number of pods/plant, pod length, number of seed/pod, 100-seed weight, single pod weight, straw yield, seed yield, and harvest index varied significantly in four mungbean genotypes. Almost all the studied parameters showed statistically identical performance at 0% and 33% leaf clipping level of the mungbean genotypes, and the least performance recorded at 66% leaf clipping. Therefore, mungbean genotypes appeared to compensate for their yield attributes up to 33% leaf clipping at 40 days after sowing. BINA moog-5 showed the preeminent tolerance against the leaf clipping among the genotypes under study.

Keywords : Leaf Clipping, BINA moog, Morphological Features.

Introduction

Pulses are essential crops for their high nutritive value, nitrogen fixation capability, and a wide range of adaptability under various cropping patterns. Per capita, daily consumption of pulse is only 14.13 g (BBS-HIES) in Bangladesh, while the World Health Organization (WHO) suggests 45 g/day for a balanced diet. Mungbean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) wikzek) is a vital pulse crop for its nutritive and economic value, which belongs to the family Leguminosae and sub-family Papilionaceae. Among the pulse crops in Bangladesh, mungbean ranks third in terms of cultivable area (102000 acres) occupied and production (35000 tons) annually (BBS, 2017). Mungbean production in Bangladesh is

challenged due to less available irrigation facilities, quality seeds, improper management practices. The yield of a crop is dependent on its source-sink capacity. Premature abscission of flowers and fruits leads to reduced sink potential is another problem for pulse production (Bari, 2000; Begum, 2002). Thus, most grain legumes, including mungbean, produce many flowers, but only a small percentage of them set pods (Fgli and Brening, 2003; Islam, 2004; Rahman, 2004). Studies of source-sink interrelationship in crop plants concluded that limitation of sink yield lies in itself, and under most circumstances, source leaves do not significantly limit sink development (Ghildiyal, 2001; Board 2004). Grain yield mostly depends upon the accumulation of dry matter in different vegetative parts and its translocation to the developing pods (Hamid et al., 1991). Source size and activity regulate the rate of dry matter accumulation.

Leaf area is a critical component that is directly related to the physiological process controlling yield and dry matter production in plants. Seed yield, in a broad sense, depends on the size, duration, and activity of the source and sink capacity. An efficient plant tends to attain optimum leaf area index (LAI) to maximize light interception immediately after germination (Kou et al., 1978). Physiological treatments such as defoliation may enhance the foliage growth, ultimately influence the dry matter accumulation before flowering and thereby the yield and yield components. Variation in the supply of assimilates through defoliation may influence the number and size of seeds per pod, ultimately the yield. Defoliation affected leaf photosynthetic rates in many crop species. The average weight of pods per 20 plants was 680.8 g with defoliation before flowering, 624.8 g, with defoliation during flowering 539.4 g after pod formation (Ramio and Oliveria, 1975). Removal of the lower leaves of soybean at the early flowering stage decline in seed yield by 20%, but it was 80% with severe defoliation (Lockwood et al., 1977).

Mungbean plant types with a maximum of two to three erect branches having shorter and thicker internodes and basal podding might be desirable for high yield potential (Tickoo et al., 1984). Vegetative growth and seed yield of mungbean were markedly decreased due to 33.3 or 66.6% removal of the leaf area, but the removal of 16.6% of leaf area had no adverse effect on yield (Pandey and Singh, 1984). In broad bean (*Viciu fuhu*), the yield was decreased by 36.7% in plants when upper leaves were removed at the beginning of flowering (Xia, 1987). Removal of 16.6% of the leaves increased the grain yield compared with no defoliation, and more than 50% defoliation markedly decreased grain yield and delayed maturity compared with other soybeans (Timisina and Thapa, 1991). Removal of flowers and pods after the first week of flowering significantly reduced yields compared to no removal (Bera and Ghosh, 1994). Plant genotypes with profuse branching habit often show poor harvest index despite high dry matter yield. In such genotypes, retention of dry

matter in vegetative organs is high and is reflected by its poor harvest index (Hamid, 1994). In cowpea, the vegetative growth and seed yield were noticeably decreased following 66% or 100% removal of the leaf area (Biswas, 2000).

There are some local and a few improved mungbean varieties in Bangladesh. The yield performance of these mungbean cultivars is not similar due to genetic variability, agronomical and physiological traits. Researches on variety development of mungbean to get improved branching, canopy structure, dry matter partitioning, and grain yield are relentlessly on progress. There is a general trend that the pulses often possess excessive vegetative growth and caused a reduction of yield (Patel et al., 1992). Defoliation up to a specific limit may be useful to overcome the problem of excess vegetative growth. Therefore, this research's objective was to investigate the effect of leaf clipping on some morphological characters, growth, and yield of four mungbeans (viz. BINA moog-5, Mutant E4I-915, Mutant N2M-402, and BINA moog -7) genotypes.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted at the field laboratory of the department of Crop Botany, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh-2202, during the period from February to May. The topography of the land was medium-high, somewhat leveled with silty loam in texture. It was more or less neutral (pH 6.32) in reaction. The experimental area experiences a subtropical climate.

Plant materials, Treatments, and Experimental design

The seeds of summer mungbean genotypes were collected from the Crop Physiology Division of Bangladesh Institute of Nuclear Agriculture (BINA), Mymensingh. The genotypes were BINA moog -5 (V1), Mutant E4I-915 (V2), Mutant N2M-402 (V3), and BINA moog - 7 (V4). Mungbean leaves are trifoliate. So, removing one leaflet from each leaf of a mungbean plant represented 33% leaf defoliation and two leaflets, 66% leaf defoliation. There were two levels of leaf clipping along with the control (no leaf clipping). Thus, there were three treatments on leaf clipping as follows: 0% leaf clipping (control, i.e., no defoliation, T₀), 33% leaf clipping (T₁), and 66% leaf clipping (T₂). The leaf clipping was furnished at 40 days after sowing (DAS) for all the genotypes. The experiment was designed in a randomized complete block design (RCBD), and each treatment was replicated three times. The individual plot size was 2m x 1m.

Seed sowing

Mungbean seeds were sown in February. Seeds were sown in lines at 20 cm apart between, and plant to plant distance was 15 cm within a row. Seeds were sown in furrows at a soil depth of about 3 cm. Intercultural operations provided according to the need of the plants.

Leaf clipping treatment

Leaf clipping was furnished in all the genotypes at 40 days after sowing when the plants were at full vegetative stage. For 33% defoliation, one leaflet, and 66% defoliation, two leaflets were removed from every trifoliate leaf in each plant of a plot using a pair of sharp scissors. During leaf clipping, care was taken to minimize injury to the plants.

Data collection

Leaf area was measured with the help of an automatic leaf area meter (Model L1-3000, USA). Other data alike, plant height (cm), number of branches /plant, number of open flower/plant, number of pods/plant, pod length (cm), number of seeds/pod, single pod weight, 100-seed weight (g), straw yield, and seed yield/plant were collected. Then harvest index (%) was calculated. Harvest index denoted the ratio of economic yield to biological yield and was calculated with the following formula (Gardner et al., 1985). The following formula calculated harvest index:

$$\text{Harvest index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Grain yield}}{\text{Biological yield}} \times 100$$

Statistical analysis

The Analysis of variances of various plant characters on growth and yield components were done following Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with the help of Computer package MSTAT (version 5.4). The mean differences among the treatments were compared by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

Results and Discussion

Effect of leaf clipping on leaf area, leaf and stem growth and dry matter

Check variety BINA moog-5 produced the highest of leaf area (685.57 cm²), leaf dry weight (1.87, 3.02 g/plant), stem dry weight (2.08, 2.37 g/plant), and total dry weight (5.85, 2.37 g/plant) (Table 1). The genotypic variation and defoliation showed a significant effect on all four mungbean genotypes, in the case of leaf area per plants, leaf and stem growth, and dry matter production (Table 1).

Table 1: Variation in leaf area and dry matter production for changes in a) genotypes and b) degree of leaf clipping in mungbean

Treatment	Leaf area(cm ²)	Dry weight (DW) at 10 days after leaf clipping			Dry weight (DW) at 10 days after leaf clipping		
		Leaf (g)	Stem(g)	Total(g)	Leaf (g)	Stem(g)	Total(g)
a) Genotypes							
BINA Moog-5	685.57 a	1.87 a	2.08 a	5.85 a	3.02	2.37 a	7.33 a
E4I-915	676.44 b	1.73 b	1.99 b	5.56 b	2.53	2.26 b	7.13 b
N2M-402	665.62 c	1.69 b	1.87 c	5.24c	2.42	2.18 c	6.82 c
BINA Moog-7	646.31 d	1.63 c	1.82 d	5.10 d	2.02	2.09 d	6.26 d
b) Degree of leaf clipping							
0% (T ₀)	1015.11 a	1.83 a	2.03 a	5.90 a	3.09 a	2.37 a	7.34 a
33% (T ₁)	664.67 b	1.57 a	1.95a	5.54 a	2.70 a	2.32 a	6.90 a
66% (T ₂)	325.67 c	1.00 b	1.72 b	4.02 b	2.22 b	1.99 b	5.91 b

Values in a column with different letter (s) differ significantly as per DMRT at 5% level of significance.

Appendix I: Analysis of variance (Mean Square) for Leaf area (cm²), leaf dry mass, stem dry mass and total dry mass at 10 days and 20 days after leaf clipping of mungbean genotypes.

Source of variation	Degrees of freedom	Leaf area (cm ²)	Leaf dry mass at 10 days after leaf clipping	Leaf dry mass 20 days after leaf clipping	Stem dry mass at 10 days after leaf clipping	Stem dry mass at 20 days after leaf clipping	Total dry mass at 10 days after leaf clipping	Total dry mass at 20 days after leaf clipping
Replication	2	2.74	0.003	0.17	0.002	0.001	0.005	0.014
Variety	3	2564.93**	0.09**	0.61**	0.12**	0.13**	1.023**	1.97**
Defoliation	2	1426089.48*	0.21**	2.33**	0.19	0.52**	6.49**	6.18**
Interaction	6	33.32	0.002	1.06 NS	0.01	0.005	0.03**	0.06**
Error	22	6.64	NS	0.25	0.001	NS	0.008	0.01
			0.003			0.002		

NS= Non significant

**Significant at 1% level of probability

*Significant at 5% level of probability

Nevertheless, there was no significant difference between T₁ and T₀ in all the parameters mentioned. Again, T₀ and T₂ treatment showed the highest and the lowest contributor to the parameters. The interaction between the genotypes and defoliation treatments was significant for the leaf area for stem dry weight at 10 DAC and the dry matter in both 10 and 20 DAC (Table 2).

Table 2. Interaction effect of genotype and clipping on leaf area (cm²), leaf and stem growth and total dry mass in four mungbean

Genotypes	Degree of leaf clipping	Leaf area and dry matter (DM) per plant at 10 days after leaf clipping				Dry matter (DM) per plant at 20 days after leaf clipping (DAC)		
		Leaf area (cm ²)	Leaf DM	Stem DM	Total DM	Leaf DM	Stem DM	Total DM
Bina-moog-5	0%	1030.51 a	1.98	2.14 a	6.22 a	3.49 b	2.53	7.75 a
	33%	683.66 d	1.90	2.08 ab	6.21 a	2.77b	2.51	7.73 a
	66%	342.53 h	1.71	2.03 c	5.10 e	2.40 b	2.09	6.52 ef
E4I-915	0%	1019.02 b	1.81	2.07 b	5.95 b	2.70 b	2.41	7.54 b
	33%	673.27 e	1.77	2.04 b	5.94 b	2.68 b	2.33	7.50 b
	66%	337.02 i	1.61	1.84 f	4.77 f	2.28 b	2.03	6.35 f
N ₂ M-402	0%	1016.56 b	1.55	1.98 e	5.76 c	2.64 b	2.31	7.21 c
	33%	659.33 f	1.74	1.98 e	5.63 cd	2.54 b	2.24	7.11 c
	66%	320.98 j	1.79	1.71 g	4.33 g	2.12 b	2.00	6.15 g
BINA Moog-7	0%	994.34 c	1.75	1.95 e	5.64 cd	2.62 b	2.24	6.88 d
	33%	642.41 g	1.69	1.92 e	5.51 d	3.53 a	2.20	6.67 e
	66%	302.18	1.45	1.61 h	4.15 h	2.03 b	1.84	5.23 h

Values in a column with different letter (s) differ significantly as per DMRT at 5% level of significance.

Leaf area index (LAI) of the green portion ultimately indicates the photo assimilates capacity. Thus, higher intensity of leaf defoliation significantly reduced the leaf area and dry matter production in Mungbean genotypes. The finding is consistent with Biswas's (2000) results, who reported that an increased degree of defoliation decreased total dry mass. Removal of expanding leaves reduced leaf area and reduced growth potential relative to non-defoliated plants (Klubertanz et al. 1986).

Effects of leaf clipping on some morphological parameters and development of reproductive parts

BINA moog-5 was a superior performer in case of morphological parameters, i.e., plant height (69.51cm), number of branches/plant (7.00), number of open flower/plant (34.54), number of pods/plant (37.35), and pod length (8.20cm) (Table 3). The morphological parameters under study was significantly affected by both the genotypic variation and defoliation (Appendix II). The interaction between the genotypes and defoliation treatments was significant in the case of plant height and the number of open flowers/plant (Table 4). Again, a higher degree of defoliation (T₂) returned the lowest output in all the parameters, while T₀ and T₁ were statistically identical in performance.

These present results agree with Biswas (2000), who reported that increased degree of defoliation at the vegetative phase could decrease plant height, number of branches/ plants, number of pods/plants,

and pod length. Hossain (2001) also reported that flower numbers per plant decreased with increasing the degree of defoliation. Genotypic variation and leaf clipping have interaction effects in plant height and number of open flowers/ plants only.

Table 3. Differences in some morphological parameters and development of reproductive part for a) genotypic variation and b) degree of leaf clipping on four mungbean genotypes

	plant height (cm)	No.of branches per plant	no of open flower/plant	number of pods/plants	length of pods (cm)
a) Genotypes					
BINA moog-5	69.51 a	7.00 a	34.54 a	37.35 a	8.20a
E ₄ I-915	66.36 b	6.56ab	3082 b	36.12 a	7.28 b
N ₂ M-402	65.50 bc	5.89 b	27.23 b	33.23 b	6.86 bc
BINA moog-7	63.58 c	6.00 b	22.74 d	29.62 c	63.42 c
b) Degree of leaf clipping					
0%	74.44 a	6.91a	33.12a	41.77 a	7.82 a
33%	72.93 a	6.67a	32.00a	40.81 a	7.57 a
66%	51.33 b	5.5b	21.37b	19.67 b	6.18 b

Values in a column with different letter (s) differ significantly as per DMRT at 5% level of significance

Appendix II: Analysis of variance (Mean Square) for plant height (cm), number of branches per plant, number of open flower per plant, number of pods per plant, length of pod (cm) of mungbean genotypes.

Source of variation	Degrees of freedom	Plant height (cm)	No. of branches/plant	No. of open flower/plant	No. of pods/plant	Length of pod (cm)
Replication	2	0.135	2.53	4.72	11.34	0.36
Variety	3	55.12**	2.39*	228.65**	106.47**	5.18**
Defoliation	2	2005.78**	6.68**	504.41**	1872.539**	9.28**
Interaction	6	14.246*	0.12NS	24.61**	3.98 NS	.06NS
Error	22	5.57	0.71	2.54	2.29	0.41

NS= Non significant

**Significant at 1% level of probability

*Significant at 5% level of probability

Table 4. Interaction effect of defoliation and mungbean genotypes on some morphological parameters and development of reproductive parts in four mungbean genotypes

Genotypes	Degree of defoliation	Plant height (cm)	Branch no./ plant	No. of open flower/ plant	Pod no. /plant	Pod length (cm)
BINA moog-5	0%	78.34 a	7.66 a	36.75a	45.48	8.73
	33%	73.32 bc	7.33 ab	35.77 ab	43.97	8.53
	66%	56.87 d	6.00 b-e	31.09 cde	22.58	7.33
E4I-915	0%	73.02 bc	7.00 abc	36.66 a	44.29	7.93
	33%	75.34 ab	7.00 abc	32.96 bcd	44.01	7.63
N ₂ M-402	66%	50.72 e	5.66 cde	22.82 f	20.07	6.27
	0%	73.04 bc	6.66 a-d	33.60 bc	40.61	7.60
	33%	73.53 bc	6.00 b-e	30.55 de	39.64	7.33
BINA moog-7	66%	49.92 e	5.00 e	17.52 g	19.45	5.63
	0%	73.37 bc	6.33 a-e	25.45 f	36.69	7.00
	33%	69.53 e	6.33 a-e	28.72 e	35.60	6.77
	66%	47.82 e	5.33 de	14.04 h	16.56	5.50

Values in a column with different letter (s) differ significantly as per DMRT at 5% level of significance

Effects of leaf clipping on yield and yield contributing characters

BINA moog-5 produced the highest of at harvest character like the number of seeds/pod (11.83), single pod weight (542.76 mg), straw yield (1433.37 Kg/ha), seed yield (795.72 Kg/ha) followed by mutant E4I-915 and N2M-402, E4I-915 produced the highest value of 100-seed weight (5.40) and highest harvest index was observed in N2M-402 (39.71) (Table 5). For all the mentioned yield contributing traits, both genetic variation and defoliation had a substantial effect (Appendix III). Biswas (2000) also reported that a decrease in pod weight and straw yield resulted from an increasing level of leaf removal for all the genotypes studied. Pandey (1983) observed that the degree of defoliation had a significant effect on the number of seeds per pod. The 100 seed weight varied among the genotypes under study, and it might be due to varieties variation. Due to the clipping of leaves, the source was limited, and enough photosynthates were not supplied to the pods. Hence, 100-seed mass might decrease with an increasing degree of defoliation. These results were in agreement with Uddin (1983), who found that an increased level of defoliation decreased 100-seed weight significantly. The seed yield was greatly influenced by variety difference and percentage defoliation, perhaps due to the increased number of pods per plant, more significant number of seeds

per pod, the most extended pod, and the highest weight of individual seed. Similar results were demonstrated by Pongkao and Yothasiri (1995), who reported that seed yield decreased with increasing defoliation.

Table 5. Differences in yield and components for a) genotypic variation and b) degree of leaf clipping in four mungbean genotypes

a) Genotypes	Number of seeds/pods	100 seeds weight (g)	Single pod weight (mg)	Straw yield (Kg/ha)	Seed yield (Kg/ha)	Harvest index (%)
BINA moog-5	11.83a	4.96 a	542.76 a	1433.37 a	795.72 a	35.77 c
E4I-915	11.29 b	5.40 a	526.36 b	1249.60 b	783.28 b	38.56 b
N ₂ M-402	10.02 c	4.47 b	512.48 c	1152.06 c	758.11 c	39.71 a
BINA moog-7	9.39 d	4.14 b	489.08d	1091.20 d	715.80 d	39.62 a
b) Degree of leaf clipping						
0%	11.24 a	5.50 a	556.71 a	1372.25 a	807.97 a	37.24 c
33%	10.99 a	5.28 a	556.71 a	1217.48 b	804.75 a	39.89 a
66%	9.67 b	3.44 b	439.58 b	1104.95 c	676.96 b	38.12 b

Values in a column with different letter (s) differ significantly as per DMRT at 5% level of significance.

Appendix III: Analysis of variance (Mean Square) for number of seeds per pod, 100 seed weight (g), single pod weight (mg), straw yield (Kg/ha), harvest index of mungbean genotypes

Source of variation	Degrees of freedom	Number of seeds per pod	100 seed weight (g)	Single pod weight (mg)	Straw yield (kg/ha)	Seed yield (kg/ha)	Harvest index
Replication	2	1.32	0.16	294.57	4388.38	0.78	1.46
Variety	3	11.37**	2.74**	4649.40*	201222.57*	11199.68**	30.43**
Defoliation	2	8.59**	15.35**	*	*	67003.060**	21.98**
Interaction	6	0.80*	1.0**	54880.08	216132.09*	141.07**	0.32 NS
Error	22	0.24	0.23	**	*	*9.56	0.97
				116.25**	2846.58NS		
				45.35	3485.23		

NS= Non significant
 **Significant at 1% level of probability
 *Significant at 5% level of probability

The interaction between the genotypes and defoliation treatments was significant in the number of seeds/pods, single pod weight, seed yield, and 100 seed weight (Table 6), which is consistent with Dewani (2000), who stated the effect of defoliation and variety on growth and yield of green pea.

Table 6. Interaction effect of leaf clipping and genotypes on yield and components in four mungbean genotypes

Genotypes	Degree of defoliation	Number of seeds/pods	100-seed weight (gm)	single pod weight (mg)	Straw yield (kg/ha)	Seed yield (Kg/ha)	Harvest index
BINA moog-5	0%	12.23 a	5.97 a	584.73a	1679.6	841.1 a	34.2
	33%	12.00 ab	5.77 ab	584.73a	1402.7	839.9 a	37.4
	66%	11.27 b-d	3.13 d	458.84e	1277.7	706.1 f	35.6
E ₄ I-915	0%	11.73 ab	5.80 ab	564.28b	1394.3	828.8 b	37.3
	33%	11.40 a-c	5.57 abc	564.28b	1223.2	828.4 b	40.4
	66%	10.73 c-e	4.83 c	450.51ef	1131.2	692.6 g	38.0
N ₂ M-402	0%	10.60 c-e	5.03 bc	546.92c	1207.6	796.4 c	38.7
	33%	10.37 de	4.80 c	546.92c	1148.4	794.8 c	40.9
	66%	9.10 f	3.57d	443.58f	1047.2	683.1 h	39.5
BINA moog-7	0%	10.40 de	5.20a-c	530.92d	1214.4	765.5 d	38.7
	33%	10.20 e	5.00 bc	530.92d	1095.6	755.8 e	40.8
	66%	7.57 g	2.23 e	405.39g	963.6	625.9 i	39.4

Values in a column with different letter (s) differ significantly as per DMRT at 5% level of significance.

Conclusion

The research focused on finding the effect of leaf clipping on different parameters of four mungbean genotype. The genotypes had significant variation at different days after leaf clipping in diverse growth and yield traits. A higher degree of leaf clipping had a more significant effect than the genotypic variation on all studied plant parameters. Finally, it seems that the imposition of the leaf clipping treatments at the early vegetative stage with the low magnitude of defoliation might give some more precise findings on the effect of source-sink limitation on growth and yield of mungbean.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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